

8T – The Riemann Hypothesis and Bosonic Compositions

O Manor

July 15, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the suggested proof of the Riemann hypothesis submitted in March 2021, in the context of bosonic fields, it is possible to make a prediction regarding bosons to propagate in odd amounts of primes. Since primes from a non-abelian group with the condition of odd amounts under addition to ensure a prime, each combination of three bosons should according to spin representation yield a new boson.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matric tensor, given by the conditions on (1.1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is wrapped in an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvature and so flatten each other, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21).

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} \frac{\partial S_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

Fermions are described by the arbitrary variation term on the main equation (1.3). By discretizing and partitioning the arbitrary variation term in (1.31), and by proving the series must have only two distinct elements that differ in sign and vanish to zero. By allowing the elements to vary, we proven they form threefold combinations.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.3)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.31)$$

In the Riemann hypothesis we have proven primes to form non-abelian group. The condition under addition was to have odd amounts of distinct higher primes, to ensure a prime. Since bosonic fields are isomorphic to prime numbers, proven by the primorial coupling constants series, it is possible to predict that compositions of odd amount of bosons will yield a new Boson.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.4)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.41)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.43)$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example the Electromagnetic coupling term:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

Bosons a in the 8T are described by net curvature, given by the term (1.45):

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.45)$$

$$\delta g = N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0$$

Take as an example three unbounded net curvatures that are distinct. $N_{V_1} = (+7)$, $N_{V_2} = (+11)$, and $N_{V_3} = (+13)$ each associated with a bosonic ripple of net curvature across the matrix tensor according to the coupling series and the setting of varying manifolds.

$$N_{V_1} + N_{V_2} + N_{V_3} = 7 + 11 + 13 \quad (1.46)$$

$$N_{V_4} = +31; N_{V_4} \in \mathbb{P} \quad (1.47)$$

The Riemann hypothesis proof than allow us to construct a theoretical framework in which we can detect those higher term bosons by combining odd amount of distinct higher primes of lower magnitude. Of course, the implicit assumption is that we need to control the process of emission and the direction of the propagation to ensure collusion, alongside to control the timing. All those elements makes it impossible to be realistic as propagation is in essence random both in direction and time. However, suppose it was possible, in that case, it would be easier to detect those higher coupling bosons, without the hadronic clusters as presented in the original formulation of the coupling series. The new term can be regarded as a superposition, or a nonlinear combination of net curvatures. Like its composing elements, the new element is unbound as well and propagate across the matrix tensor.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)